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The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region

EUVIP

Overview of Op-eds Published within the EUVIP Project

1. 1. 2023 – 31. 12. 2025

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Overview of the project

Project title	The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region
Project acronym	EUVIP
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Program	HORIZON.4.1 - Widening participation and spreading excellence HORIZON.4.1.2 - Twinning
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Website	www.euvip-project.com
Coordinator	Palacký University Olomouc (UP), ROR: 04qxnmv42 University of Helsinki (UH), ROR: 040af2s02
Partners	UCLouvain (UCL), ROR: 02495e989 University of Copenhagen, ROR: 035b05819 (until 2023-08-31) Lund University, ROR: 012a77v79 (from 2023-11-01)
Start date	2023-01-01
End date	2025-12-31
Project summary	<p>Through its concise training, research, communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities EUVIP will significantly contribute to shaping the new, rapidly developing academic field of Indo-Pacific Studies. The project will raise the awareness of the stakeholders (academia, civil society, politics, and broad public) of the strategic, political, and economic significance of the volatile Indo-Pacific region for Europe and for a values-based European approach towards this region. Together with its seven dissemination partners, the EUVIP consortium will create a sustainable European Indo-Pacific experts network and knowledge hub with strong dissemination channels to national and EU policymakers in order to strongly contribute to the EU's Indo-Pacific strategy and policies. In addition, EUVIP will establish a Myanmar Centre at Palacky University in Olomouc (Czech Republic) to connect academia with politics and the civil society. EUVIP will build on UP's strong expertise on Southeast Asia and China's Belt and Road Initiative, supplemented by the</p>

complementary expertise of three leading European research partners (University of Helsinki, University of Copenhagen, and Université Catholique de Louvain). To further improve UP's excellence capacity and resources, the three expert partners will provide training to UP's early career researchers, PhD students, and research management administrators. This transfer of knowledge will result in a much higher international visibility of UP academics through an increased number of publications in world-class journals, an increased number of Horizon 2020 project applications, an increased reputation and attractiveness of UP for renowned international scholars and students, and increased mobility and employability of the UP staff.

Overview of op-eds

Op-ed goal

Disseminate, communicate and exploit the innovative research results in EUVIP member states and at EU level

Related to

Project objective 4, Work package 4 (Task 4.2)

List of op-eds published by project member

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3. **Kironska, Kristina; Lubina, Michal**; *What Do Bangladeshis Really Think of the Rohingya?*; The Diplomat; 2023-02-15; <https://thediplomat.com/2023/02/what-do-bangladeshis-really-think-of-the-rohingya/>
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5. **Ware, Anthony; Kironska, Kristina**; *As Rohingya crisis worsens, public support is high in Australia and New Zealand to take them in*; South China Morning Post; 2023-03-02; <https://www.scmp.com/week-asia/opinion/article/3212038/rohingya-crisis-worsens-public-support-high-australia-and-new-zealand-take-them>
6. **Kironska, Kristina**; *'V4' relations solid, but need a boost*; Taipei Times; 2023-03-24; <https://www.taipeitimes.com/News/editorials/archives/2023/03/24/2003796629>
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12. **Kironska, Kristina**; *Myanmar's Struggle for Freedom Three Years After the Military Coup*; Reset Dialogues on Civilizations; 2024-02-22; <https://www.resetdoc.org/story/myanmar-struggle-freedom-three-years-after-military-coup/>
13. **Kironska, Kristina**; *Finding Hope in Chaos: Myanmar Entering its Fourth Year Post-Coup [在混亂中找到希望：緬甸進入第4年的後政變時代]*; Generation Now Asia; 2024-03-21; NA
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16. **Broul, David; Nenutil, Antonín**; *Potřebuje Indonésie Evropskou unii? Možný vývoj zahraniční politiky pod novým prezidentem Prabowo Subiantem*; Institute of International Relations Prague; 2024-11-17; <https://www.iir.cz/potrebuje-indonesie-evropskou-unii-mozny-vyvoj-zahranicni-politiky-pod-novym-prezidentem-prabowo-subiantem>
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